

Salts of Metal Ions with Organic Arsonic Acids. Part VII. Salts of Nickel(II) with Arylarsonic Acids

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The polymeric salts of nickel(II) with phenylarsonic acid derivatives of 1:1 stoichiometry have been prepared and characterized by elemental analysis, magnetic susceptibility and IR and reflectance spectral data. Octahedral structure is proposed for all the salts except in case of *o*-nitrophenylarsonate where distorted tetrahedral structure is suggested.

THE study of arsonic acids and their salts is of theoretical as well as practical importance. These acids and their salts are being used as pesticides¹ to protect crops from pathological diseases, to treat chickens from protozoal infection² and to fight histomoniasis³ and other diseases^{4,5}. They have also been used as analytical reagents^{6,7} in laboratory. Since transition metals are essential in plant nutrition⁸, it was thought desirable to study the salts of arsonic acids with these metals.

Pietsch⁹ studied the *pH* values at which the precipitation of nickel and other metal ions occurred with different arsonic acids. Basato and Peloso¹⁰ studied the complexes of cobalt (II), nickel (II) and copper (II) with a Schiff base containing two arsonic acid groups. Salts of nickel (II) with methylarsonic acid¹¹, *o*-aminophenylarsonic acid^{12,13} and phenylarsonic acid¹³ have been reported.

In continuation of our studies on salts of phenylarsonic acids¹³⁻¹⁹, salts of nickel(II) with arylarsonic acids have been isolated and their elemental analysis, magnetic susceptibilities at room temperature and IR and electronic spectra are being reported.

Experimental

Arylarsonic acids have been prepared by reported methods.^{20,21} For obtaining a salt, alcoholic solutions of an arylarsonic acid (0.01 mole) and nickel acetate (0.01 mole, Riedel) were mixed and refluxed for about half an hour, when the green precipitate separated. The precipitate was filtered, washed repeatedly with hot alcohol and dried under vacuum.

Estimation of carbon, hydrogen and halogens was carried out by Australian Microanalytical Service, Melbourne. Nickel was estimated volumetrically using EDTA as a titrant.

The IR spectra of acids and salts were recorded as Nujol mulls on a Hilger and Watts H.800 Spectrophotometer (range 4000-650 cm^{-1}) using sodium chloride optics. The electronic reflectance spectra of salts were recorded on Unicam SP 700 A UV and Visible Spectrophotometer having SP 735 diffuse reflectance attachment (range 50,000-4000 cm^{-1}).

The magnetic susceptibilities of the salts were measured at room temperature using Gouy method. The diamagnetic corrections were calculated on the basis of Pascal's constants.²²

Results and Discussions

On the basis of elemental analysis (Table 1), the arylarsonates of nickel may be represented by the general formula, $\text{X.C}_6\text{H}_4\text{AsO}_3.\text{Ni}.n\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where $n=0, 1/2, 1$ or $3/2$ and $\text{X}=p\text{-CH}_3, p\text{-Cl}, p\text{-Br}, p\text{-OCH}_3, o\text{-OCH}_3$ or $o\text{-COOH}$, except in the case of *o*-nitrophenylarsonate, where the empirical formula is $\text{O}_2\text{N.C}_6\text{H}_4\text{AsO}_3.\text{Ni}.1/2\text{-C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$.

In the IR spectra of acids, $\nu(\text{OH})$ occurs around 2750 and 2250 cm^{-1} ²³, while in the spectra of salts, these bands are absent, indicating the bonding of both oxygens of $\text{As}\begin{matrix} \diagup \text{O} \\ \diagdown \text{O} \end{matrix}$ with nickel (II). This suggestion is further supported by the variation in the symmetric and asymmetric stretching frequencies²⁴ (Table 2) of $\text{As}\begin{matrix} \diagup \text{O} \\ \diagdown \text{O} \end{matrix}$ on salt formation. The $\nu(\text{As}=\text{O})$ which occurs around 935-845 cm^{-1} in arsonic acids, is shifted by 20-100 cm^{-1} towards lower frequency in the salts of *p*-methyl-, *p*-chloro-, *p*-methoxy- and *o*-nitrophenylarsonic acids. A similar shift is observed in the salts of *p*-bromo-, *o*-methoxy- and *o*-carboxyphenylarsonic acids as well but the shifted bands are not clearly discernible as they overlap with the bands

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TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF THE SALTS

Sr. No.	Salt	Calculated (%)				Found (%)				$\mu_{\text{eff.}}$ (B.M.)
		C	H	X*	Ni	C	H	X*	Ni	
1.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ AsO ₃ Ni	30.80	2.57	—	21.53	31.51	3.05	—	21.1	3.21
2.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ AsO ₃ Ni.H ₂ O	23.13	1.93	11.4	18.87	23.67	2.03	11.5	18.5	3.07
3.	<i>p</i> -Br.C ₆ H ₄ AsO ₃ Ni	21.32	1.19	23.7	17.38	21.64	1.85	23.3	17.5	3.03
4.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ AsO ₃ Ni.H ₂ O	27.39	2.93	—	19.12	27.94	3.04	—	18.9	3.25
5.	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ AsO ₃ Ni.1/2H ₂ O	28.28	2.69	—	19.72	28.73	3.56	—	19.6	3.20
6.	<i>o</i> -COOH.C ₆ H ₄ AsO ₃ Ni.3/2H ₂ O	25.48	2.43	—	17.80	25.81	3.42	—	18.0	3.33
7.	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ AsO ₃ Ni.1/2C ₂ H ₅ OH	25.71	2.14	—	17.97	24.99	2.06	—	18.1	2.90

X* = Cl or Br

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA OF ARYLARSONIC ACIDS AND THEIR SALTS

Sr. No.	Acid	As $\begin{matrix} \diagup \\ \text{O} \\ \diagdown \end{matrix}$		AsO ₃ frequencies			As-C(<i>aromatic</i>) stretch		Substituent group (in benzene ring) stretches		
		Smym. stretch Acid	Salt	Asym. stretch Acid	Salt	As=O stretch Acid	Salt	Acid	Salt	Acid	Salt
1.	<i>p</i> -Methyl-phenylarsonic acid	765m	780m	785m	780m	845m, 865m	825m	1090s	1100s	—	—
2.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenylarsonic acid	755m	735m	825m	780s	900m 915m	822s	1077s	1087s	1077s	1087s
3.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenylarsonic acid.	765m	780s	812m	820s	915m 935m	820s	1085w	1090w	1065m	1065s
4.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenylarsonic acid	755m	785mb	790m	785mb	890mb	825s	1095s	1100s	1015s 1257s	1025s 1250s
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenylarsonic acid	790m	765w	860w	810sb	910s	810sb	1125m	1125m	1010s 1235m	1015m 1255m
6.	<i>o</i> -Carboxyphenylarsonic acid	785m	745m	820w	835mb	855m	835mb	1085s	1115wb	1300s 1410w 3100wb 1637m 1650m	1305w 1410w 3100w 1550m 1600m
7.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenylarsonic acid.	780m	780w	840w	805w	905s	870m	1105m	1095m	1330m 1515s	1330m 1515s

TABLE 3—ASSIGNMENTS OF ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS (CM⁻¹) AND CALCULATED VALUES OF LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS (CM⁻¹)

Sr. No.	Salt	³ T _{2g} (F)← ³ A _{2g} (F)	³ T _{1g} (F)← ³ A _{2g} (F)	³ T _{1g} (P)← ³ A _{2g} (F)	Dq	B
1.	p-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ AsO ₃ Ni	8230	13510	23530	823	827
2.	p-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ AsO ₃ Ni.H ₂ O	8064	13330	23120	806	815
3.	p-Br.C ₆ H ₄ AsO ₃ Ni	8330	13790	23900	833	843
4.	p-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ AsO ₃ Ni.H ₂ O	8200	13330	23320	820	816
5.	o-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ AsO ₃ Ni.1/2 H ₂ O	8200	13700	23650	820	841
6.	o-COOH.C ₆ H ₄ AsO ₃ Ni.3/2 H ₂ O	8060	13990	23700	806	860
7.	o-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ AsO ₃ Ni.1/2 C ₃ H ₇ OH	³ T ₂ (F)← ³ T ₁ (F) 4000	³ A ₂ (F)← ³ T ₁ (F) 8400	³ T ₁ (F)← ³ T ₁ (F) 13160	448	653

(835-810 cm⁻¹) due to As $\begin{matrix} \diagup \\ \text{O} \\ \diagdown \end{matrix}$ asymmetric stretch. This downward shift may be ascribed to tridentate nature of AsO₃ group in these salts.

The symmetric and asymmetric stretching frequencies of H₃C-O-C_{aromatic} group appearing at 1010 and 1235 cm⁻¹ respectively in *o*-methoxyphenylarsonic acid shift to 1015 and 1255 cm⁻¹ respectively on the formation of a salt, indicating thereby the participation in bonding of -OCH₃ group with nickel(II).

In the spectrum of *o*-carboxyphenylarsonic acid the bands at 3100, 1410 and 1300 cm⁻¹ may be assigned²⁶ to ν(OH), δ(OH) and ν(C=O) respectively. A doublet at 1650, 1637 cm⁻¹ arises due to ν(C=O)²⁶. Elemental analysis suggests that the proton of carboxylic acid group is not removed in salt formation. This is further supported by the presence of bands, though of weak intensities, at 3100, 1410 and 1305 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of the salt. However, the doublet at 1650, 1637 cm⁻¹ of the acid shifts to 1610, 1550 cm⁻¹ in the salt, indicating coordination of oxygen of C=O with nickel(II).

In *p*-bromo- and *o*-nitrophenylarsonates there is no change in the frequencies of substituted bromo and nitro groups. However, in the case of *p*-chloro- and *p*-methoxyphenylarsonates, a slight change in the position of bands of substituted groups is observed.

The results of magnetic susceptibility and electronic spectral studies of the salts at room temperature are given in Tables 1 and 3 respectively. Except *o*-nitrophenylarsonate, all other salts of nickel(II) have

magnetic moment in the range 3.11-3.35 BM. These values correspond to octahedral nickel(II) complexes²⁷. The reflectance spectra confirm this conclusion. The assignment of various transitions to the observed bands are given in Table 3. Using the method of Lever²⁷, the values of Dq and B have been calculated. The ranges for the values of Dq and B in our salts are 806-833 cm⁻¹ and 815-860 cm⁻¹ respectively. These values almost correspond with the values of Dq=821 and B=875 cm⁻¹ for octahedral phenylphosphonate of nickel, C₆H₅PO₃Ni, found by Grignonneau and coworkers²⁸. Thus phenylphosphonic acid and arylarsonic acids have almost equal ligand field strength and nephelauxetic effect.

The reflectance spectrum of *o*-nitrophenylarsonate of nickel(II) differs from those of other salts. Where as in other salts the three observed bands are approximately at 8100, 13,700 and 23,700 cm⁻¹, in *o*-nitrophenylarsonate the bands are observed at 840, 13,200 and 31,250 cm⁻¹. The highest energy band has got high intensity, indicating it to be a charge transfer band. There are, therefore, only two ligand field bands in this salt. Absence of a ligand field band around 24,000 cm⁻¹ and the magnetic moment value of 2.9 BM, which is characteristic of a distorted tetrahedral stereochemistry²² for nickel(II), suggest that this salt does not have octahedral geometry. Assuming a tetrahedral stereochemistry of nickel(II) in this salts, the bands can be assigned to transitions as :

$${}^3A_2(F) \leftarrow {}^3T_1(F), \nu_2 = 8400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$$

$${}^3T_1(P) \leftarrow {}^3T_1(F), \nu_3 = 13,160 \text{ cm}^{-1}$$

The values of $Dq = 448 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $B = 652 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are calculated on the basis of graphical method of Lever²⁷ for tetrahedral nickel(II) complexes. The band for the transition, ${}^3T_2(F) \leftarrow {}^3T_1(F)$, calculated on the basis of experimental values of ν_2 and ν_3 and calculated values of Dq and B should be at 3920 cm^{-1} . This band is found at 4000 cm^{-1} in the IR spectrum of the salt.

Thus the elemental analysis, magnetic data and electronic spectral study suggest a polymeric nature for these salts. This conclusion is substantiated by high melting points and insolubility of the salts in water and most of organic solvents.

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